

Impact of Literacy on Working Population in Kushinagar District, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

Literacy and workforce are the two main factors for the social and economic development of people, community, society, region and country. This study analyses the trend and pattern of literacy and workforce participation in Kushinagar district, U.P. over the last decade (2001 to 2011). The study also tries to find out the correlation between literacy and workforce participation for both the Census years of 2001 and 2011. The data has been collected from the secondary sources (mainly from District Census Handbook of Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011). Spearman's Rank correlation has been used to find out the correlation between the literacy and workforce participation of the study area. The data has been analysed in MS excel software and the location map has been prepared on ArcGIS 10.1. Analysis of the data shows a negative correlation existing between literacy and workforce participation in the study area. The major finding reveals that, the trend in literacy is increasing whereas the workforce participation has been decreased during the last decade due to the population increase which leads to the declination of job opportunities.

Keywords : literacy, workforce participation, spearman's rank correlation, social and economic development.

Introduction

The literacy in the Kushinagar district has been increasing over the years but the workforce participation is decreasing in the same period which is the major problem to be concerned. Literacy is one of the key factor for the improvement of socio-economic status of people, community, society and a country. Literacy in India has been increasing over the years but a vast disparity exist among regions, social groups and also between genders. Among the social groups the Dalits have lower literacy apart from the Muslim women but they will serve as a catalyst in the development if they will be given equal opportunities in education (Benzamin, 2008).

Literates are defined as persons aged seven or above who can both read and write with understanding in any language is considered as literates (Census of India). Literacy plays an important role for getting jobs and keeping it, it also helps in skill development more easily than the illiterate ones. Literacy is very essential to achieve a highly skilled or technical workforce which also leads a country to strong economic development.

Workforce participation can be defined as the percentage of total working population including main and marginal workers in a population (Census of India). Any person who is em-

employed and having high education level have very less chance to be unemployed, on the other hand unemployed person's education has very less impact on employment chances (Husted et.al 2001).

The level of child mortality rate is very low among working women in comparison to non-working women, so there is a negative relation between woman employment and survival her child (Basu and Basu, 1991). The increase in population growth has led to the complication in attainment of thorough education in some of the Indian states, while some states are already experiencing suppress in school age (Dyson, Cassen and Visaria, 2005). The overall literacy of Kushinagar district has been recorded as 45.80% in 2001 and 64.75% in 2011 Census years respectively whereas male and female literacy were 62.8% and 28.3% during 2001 census which increased to 77.51% and 51.59% in

2011 Census. So there is a huge gap between male and female literacy in the district. The situation of female literacy in the district is slightly improved during last decade but it is still lagging far behind to male literacy till the date. According to 2001 and 2011 Census, the total workforce participation in the district was 34.7% and 31.5% respectively. In 2001 Census, male and female workforce participation has been recorded as 45.6% and 23.3% respectively which has decreased to 44.3% and 18.3% respectively during 2011 Census. The district shows an increase in literacy but the workforce participation for both male and female has been decreased over the study period (2001 to 2011). The objectives of the study are to analyse the trend of literacy and workforce participation, to find out the impact of literacy on workforce participation and to explain the relationship between literacy and increase in workforce participation in the study area.

Figure 1: Location and administrative units of the study area

Source: District Census Handbook Kushinagar, 2011

Study Area

Kushinagar is a part of Gorakhpur division in eastern Uttar Pradesh, and the district head-quarter is located at Padrauna town. The district is famous for the Mahaparinirvana (in 400 BCE) of Mahatma Buddha. Since 13th May, 1994, the district came into existence, earlier it was a part of Deoria district. The district has an area of 2,905 Square Kilometres; it is bounded by Bihar State in the East, Deoria in the South, Gorakhpur district on the West and Maharjganj district in the North-West. The climate in the study area remain extremely hot in summer and moderately cold during the winter season. At present, the district has been divided into six sub divisions including Padrauna, Kasia, Hata, Tamkuhi Raj, Khadda and Kaptanganj. The district has been also divided into fourteen Community Development Blocks namely Kaptanganj, Ramkola, Motichak, Hata, Sukrauli, Khadda, Nebuwa Naurangiya, Vishunpura, Padrauna, Kasiya, Dudhai, Fazilnagar, Tamkuhi Raj and Sevarahi (fig.1). According to the 2011 Census, Kushinagar district has a population of 35,64,544 persons among these, 18,18,055 are males and 17,46,489 are females and has a sex ratio of 961 females per 1000 males.

The district has a population density of 1226 inhabitants per square kilometre. Its population growth rate over the decade 2001-2011 was 23.08% in which 23.37% are male growth rate whereas female has a growth rate of 23.03%. The district has population majorly belonging to Hindu and Muslim religion consisting of 82.16% and 17.40% of population respectively. Agriculture is the main occupation of the rural people because the industrialization is negligible in the district. Kushinagar district has been chosen as study area because it is one of the district which is lagging behind in literacy as well as in workforce participation in comparison to state as well as country. The Kushinagar district is one of the 250 most backward district in

India demarcated by government of India.

Data Sources and Methodology

Whole study is primarily based on secondary data sources, which were collected from the Census of India and other publications. The data of the decadal change from 2001 to 2011 had been collected from the District Census Handbook of Kushinagar District of 2001 and 2011, Primary Census Abstract (PCA), General Population Tables, books and articles. Block is considered as the basic unit of this study. The data has been analysed in Microsoft excel. The analysis and interpretation has been done through textual and tabular formats followed by the result and discussions. The block wise variation has been shown with the help of tables and maps. The maps have been prepared on ARC GIS 10.1. The analysis of the data has been done to understand trend of literacy and workforce participation. The correlation between literacy and workforce participation has been calculated by using Spearman's Rank Correlation coefficient method. The Spearman's Rank Correlation-formula is as follows:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{\{6\sum d^2\}}{(n^3-n)}$$

Where,

r_s = spearman's rank correlation, d = difference between ranks of the two variables, and n = the number of samples.

The value of the correlation lies between -1 to 1 i.e. $-1 < r < 1$. This is done by ranking the two variables and calculating by using the formula to find out the correlation between the two variables to test the hypothesis by using the level of significance methods. The study has been focused only in rural area hence it cannot be applicable in urban places. The work done in house or work in own field have not been considered as employed workers.

Results and Discussion Spatio- temporal changes in Literacy (2001-

2011)

Literacy varies from country to country, region to region, community to community, social groups to social groups and family to family. According to Census of India, as far as our country is concerned the total literacy in the year 2011 was 74.04% of which 82.00% were male and 65.46% were females. There is an increase of 9.19% in literacy from 2001 to 2011 can be seen. The literacy has been increased in both male and female but the disparity has been increased as well. If we look at the total literacy of U.P. (67.68%) which is less than the country's total literacy in which male and female literacy stand as 77.28% and 57.18% respectively.

In Kushinagar district, the total literacy in

the year 2011 is 64.75% (male 77.51% and female 51.59%) which is less than national as well as state average. There is an increase of 22.18% in literacy in between 2001 to 2011 Census years. The literacy has been increased due to the improvement of infrastructure facilities like increase in number of Schools, mid-day meal scheme, awareness among people, etc.

The spatial pattern of the blocks shows that Hata (54.00%) has the highest literacy whereas Khadda(34.10%) has the lowest literacy in 2001 Census. According to 2011 Census, Hata and Fazinagar have the highest literacy with 69.88% whereas Dudhahi (58.27%) has the lowest literacy among the blocks (table 1) which also shows that Khadda (23.90%) recorded the highest change in literacy while Hata (15.88%)

Table 1: Spatio-Temporal changes in Literacy and Workforce Participation

Kushinagar Blocks	Literacy rate in 2001(%)	Literacy rate in 2011 (%)	Decadal Change (%)	Total workersin 2001(%)	Total workersin 2001(%)	Decadal Change (%)
Khadda	34.10	58.00	23.90	37.90	35.20	-2.70
NebuaNaurangiya	42.50	63.98	21.48	40.80	31.50	-9.30
Vishunpura	41.50	61.71	20.21	36.40	31.60	-4.60
Padrauna	49.10	66.07	16.97	32.90	29.50	-3.40
Kaptanganj	50.00	68.50	18.50	33.40	31.00	-2.40
Ramkola	45.30	64.79	19.49	36.00	23.4	-12.60
Motichak	47.30	67.50	20.20	35.70	32.90	-2.80
Sukrauli	50.80	68.56	17.76	38.50	37.50	-1.00
Hata	54.00	69.88	15.88	34.30	30.60	-3.70
Kasiya	52.60	68.90	16.30	31.00	30.10	-0.90
Fazilnagar	52.60	69.88	17.28	30.90	33.90	3.00
Tamkuhi Raj	50.90	67.85	16.95	28.90	29.70	0.80
Dudhahi	35.10	57.28	22.18	35.40	32.40	-3.00
Sevrahi	38.60	58.98	20.38	35.00	32.30	-2.70
Total	45.80	64.75	18.95	34.70	31.50	-3.20

Source: District Census Handbook, Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011

showed the lowest change. The trend of literacy change has also showed in fig. 2 which has been divided in four class intervals low (below 43%), moderate (43%-52%), highly moderate (52%-61%) and high (above 61%) whereas the gap has also been divided in four class intervals low (below 19%), moderate (19%-21%), highly moderate (21%-23%) and high (above 23%).The literacy in 2011 has been recorded increase in all the blocks in Kushinagar district (fig. 2).

The reasons for the increase in literacy are changes in infrastructure such as increasing number of schools, mid-day meal scheme, awareness among the people about education, etc. among all the blocks in the district only two blocks i.e. Fazilnagar (3%) and Tamkuhi Raj (0.8%) show positive changes in the workforce

participation and apart from these two blocks all other blocks show negative change during last decade (2001-2011) in which Ramkola has the lowest (-12.70%) change. The decrease in workforce participation has been observed because a large number of population has been added to the total population whereas the work/job opportunities has not increased much.

Spatio- temporal changes in Workforce Participation (2001-2011)

The size of workforce is determined by the working population between the age group of 15-64 years. The workforce participation of India is 39.8% in which 53.26% are male and 25.51% are females (2011). The total workforce participation at the state level is 33.4% of which 47.4% are male and 18.3% are females in 2011

Source: District Census Handbook, Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011

Figure 2: Literacy in Kushinagar District, U.P.

Census. The 2011 Census data of Kushinagar district shows that 31.5% are the total working population which was 34.7% during previous Census year. Result reveals the decreasing trend in workforce participation i.e. -3.2%. The district has lower workforce participation in comparison to state and national average. The spatial and temporal variation in the study area shows that Nebua Naurangiya (40.8%) has the highest share of working population whereas TamkuhiRaj (28.9%) has the lowest workforce participation in 2001 Census. According to 2011 Census, Sukrauli (37.5%) block recorded the highest and Padrauna (29.7%) has the lowest workforce participation. The trend of workforce participation and change has also showed in fig. 3 which has been divided in four class intervals low (below 27%), moderate (27%-31%), highly

moderate (31%-35%) and high (above 35%) whereas the gap has been divided in three class intervals low (below -6%), moderate (-6%-0%) and high (above 0%). Here, there are twelve blocks which have shown negative growth in workforce participation whereas only two blocks has shown positive growth in the district.

Male-Female statistics of literacy and workforce participation (2001-2011)

The composition of male-female literacy and workforce participation shows a disparity in between the variables. The mean literacy of male (78%) in 2011 show an increase from 2001 (63.27%) whereas the mean female literacy in 2001 was 28.33% which increased to 51.83% in 2011. But there is a large gap found between male and female literacy during the last decade.

Source: District Census Handbook, Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011

Figure 3: Workforce participation in Kushinagar district

The male literacy in 2001 shows a deviation of 7.61 whereas females shows a deviation of 6.42 which has decreased in the 2011 Census, the male and female literacy has a deviation from 6.81 and 4.72 respectively in 2011.

The minimum literacy of male and female in 2001 were 48.6% and 18.2% respectively showing wide gap in the literacy level. The maximum literacy of male (72.7%) is double than female (36.5%) in 2001. But the minimum and maximum literacy in the year 2011 for both the genders showed an improvement and the gap between them has also improved (table 2). The

mean workforce participation of male and female also showed a wide gap in both the Census years but 2011 census data showed that the gap has shortened. The deviation in workforce participation in male (2.3 to 1.8) and female (4.3 to 3.8) has been improved from 2001 to 2011 Census.

Minimum and maximum workforce participation has decreased for both male and female but the gap is still remained high between the genders (table 2). The major factors responsible for the gap between male and female literacy

Table 2: Male-Female statistics of literacy and workforce participation

Variables	Category	Year	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Literacy	Male	2001	63.27	7.61	48.6	72.7
	Female		28.33	6.42	18.2	36.5
	Male	2011	78	6.81	70.07	83.15
	Female		51.83	4.72	43.81	57.28
Workforce Participation Rate	Male	2001	45.6	2.3	41.4	48.7
	Female		23.5	4.3	16.5	32.3
	Male	2011	31.5	1.8	41.2	47.4
	Female		18.18	3.8	13.5	27.7

Source: District Census Handbook, Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011

as well as workforce participation are poverty, gender bias, education of parents, accessibility, child marriage, society, government policies, etc.

Correlation between Literacy and Workforce Participation

Spearman's Rank correlation method is adopted to correlate between literacy and workforce participation for both of the census years. The calculation reveals that there is a negative correlation (i.e. $r_s = -0.59$) in 2001 between the literacy and workforce participation. So the negative correlation between literacy and workforce participation means that the null hy-

pothesis has been accepted and it can be said that there is no significant relationship between literacy and workforce participation in the year 2001. The negative correlation shows that the literacy has increased but the working population has remained unemployed.

The correlation between literacy and workforce participation in 2011 shows that there is a weak negative correlation ($r_s = -0.13$) between literacy and workforce participation. Here, the negative correlation proved that the hypothesis has been accepted which also proved that there is no significant relation between literacy and increase in workforce participation in 2011.

The main reason for the negative correlation is that the literacy has been increased but the job opportunities still stagnant.

The working population belongs to the age group of 15-64 years (Census of India). This age group plays vital role of population dividend and also an important source of income. The share of workforce participation define the economic status of any country, more the share of workforce will signify more the level of development. In the study area, the correlation between literacy and workforce has shown negative correlation in both the Census year 2001 and 2011 but there is an improvement in correlation which has been observed during the decade from 2001 (-0.59) to 2011 (-0.13) which indicate that in the coming years there might be positive correlation between literacy and workforce will be observe. The literacy has shown an increasing trend during the last decade (2001-2011) in every blocks whereas the workforce participation has shown decreasing trend in all the blocks except two blocks (Fazilnagar and Tamkuhi Raj) during the same decade.

Conclusion

Workforce Participation is one of the most important factor of production and it plays the primary role in thorough economic development for any country. Hence, the size of the workforce participation shows the economic productiveness of any country. The study shows that the trend in literacy is positively increased during the decade 2001 to 2011 but the workforce participation shows a negative growth during the last decade, only two blocks (Fazilnagar and Tamkuhi Raj) showed positive growth in workforce participation. The correlation between the literacy and workforce participation showed negative correlation in both the years 2001 (-0.59) and 2011 (-0.13). But, an improvement in the correlation between literacy

and workforce participation has been observed during the last decade. The reason for the negative correlation is that in Kushinagar district population has increased but the job/employment opportunities has not increased. The negative correlation is also due to the fact that for workforce, skill is an important factor but literacy might not be. The decreasing trend in workforce participation is not an encouraging sign for the development not only for the people but also for the district as well as for the state and country. The females are lagging far behind males both in term of literacy and workforce participation and it leads to a stagnation for sustainable and inclusive development of any region. Government should provide job opportunities for the people especially for women so that the share of working population can increase and also leads to the improvement in quality of life of the people. For the inclusive development of the people, it is necessary to be well educated and well employed. Though government has formulated many programs and policies for education as well as for employment but it needs to be implemented in such a way that each and everyone in the working age group will be benefited.

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